

DTO-BioFlow

Integration of biodiversity monitoring
data into the Digital Twin Ocean

dto-bioflow.eu

**EXPLORE MORE
USE CASES**

From Data to Decisions: DTO-BioFlow Use Cases

DUC 3 - Integrated Monitoring of
Pelagic Biodiversity and Human Impact

Funded by
the European Union

From Insight to Impact

The Demonstrator Use Cases (DUCs) are at the heart of the DTO-BioFlow initiative, translating complex scientific capabilities into tangible digital solutions for marine biodiversity monitoring and management.

Designed to showcase the power of an **end-to-end digital approach**, these use cases connect cutting-edge biodiversity observations with AI-enhanced models, analytical tools, and the infrastructure of the Digital Twin of the Ocean (DTO).

Each DUC serves as a living example of how real-world marine challenges can be addressed through integrated digital workflows. They all address a pressing challenge for ocean sustainability and proposes an integrated, evidence-based solution.

DUC 3 focuses on the assessing pelagic biodiversity and human impact.

Plankton play a foundational role in ocean ecosystems and are highly sensitive to environmental change. This use case enhances biodiversity assessments by integrating traditional microscopy, automated imaging, and genetic methods **to better track plankton diversity** and **assess how it is affected by human pressures** such as climate change and pollution.

Challenge

Current plankton monitoring is limited in resolution and scope.

Traditional microscopy methods are time-consuming and often miss shifts in species composition, making it difficult to detect and interpret changes caused by human activities.

Solution

This DUC enhances biodiversity monitoring by integrating microscopy, imaging, and genetic data with environmental context.

The integration of these approaches provides a more complete picture of pelagic diversity and enables improved indicators to assess the effects of human pressures on marine ecosystems

Data and monitoring networks used

Imaging and genetic data, environmental data.

Expected Outputs

Improved Plankton diversity indicators for MSFD and OSPAR reporting

Analytical insights on how human activities affect pelagic ecosystems and their functions

Digital Twin Capabilities Demonstrated.

- **Data integration:** Merges novel biological and environmental data for ecosystem-scale assessments
- **Impact analysis:** Links human pressures to changes in plankton diversity and ecosystem function
- **Gap identification:** Highlights limitations in current pelagic monitoring and indicator systems

Useful for

- Marine monitoring agencies
- Environmental researchers and institutions

Learn more on development and read the publications

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Consortium

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